

ETHNO-CULTURAL ASPECTS OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

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ANNOTATION

National cultures are created in the process of finding ways to overcome the difficulties of living in the natural location, geography and climate of the area where each nation or people lives, and later become national customs and traditions. Our national traditions and unique traditions have been polished for many years and are rising to their highest level, and we can witness that these processes have become an integral part of our country's policy and have become an example of today's reforms.

Key words: social progress, ethnoculture, Turkic peoples.

The Uzbek nation, as the main link of the Turkic peoples, is considered one of the major nations that has experienced a long historical process. It is a fact that Uzbekistan is geographically located in a very convenient place. The qualities of generosity, hospitality, honesty, loyalty, purity, and courtesy inherited by the Uzbek people from the long historical past are considered the most important aspects of the national character. That is why qualities such as restraint, patience, and tolerance have been passed down from generation to generation in our national character. It is not for nothing that countries in history dreamed of owning the regions of the seven climates of the world. In ancient times, countries were defined by their territorial area, the number and size of their army, and the wealth of flora and fauna there. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur in his "Baburnoma" also mentions Mavoraunnahr as being in the fourth and fifth climate. He says that India is in the first, second and third climate. Today's scientists use the word "region" instead of

the word "climate". All nations and peoples scattered around the world engage in activities necessary for life based on the climate and geographical possibilities of the area where they live. On the one hand, the fact that the peoples of Central Asia lived in an area with high potential points to the fact that they created great innovations in the fields of production, science, art, and culture. It is reported that many canals, bridges, fortress walls, and communication structures built in the history of our country were built with the help of hashar. Unlike the ancient Egyptians, the peoples of Central Asia made great changes in the field of agriculture. While the representatives of the settled population who lived in our country made a living cultivating the land and growing various agricultural products, large clans such as Kungiro, Lokai, Qarluq, Turk, who migrated from Dashti Kipchak, were engaged in all kinds of animal husbandry. Historical sources show that great cultures were created in our country through these production areas, and this culture was gradually exported to the whole world through trade routes. In the book "Bizkim, Uzbeklar" by one of the great writers of our time, Abdukakhor Ibrohimov, in the two-volume book "The World Encyclopedia dictionary Book", which was published in Chicago, USA, with 200,000 copies, he told the Uzbek nation that "Uzbeks are one of the oldest peoples among the peoples of the world. The nation that settled first among the Turkic peoples, lived culturally, and contributed to world civilization...|| [4:27] - certainly pleases all of us. It should be noted with pleasure that noble virtues and aspirations are embedded in the blood and bones of our people. The high spirituality characteristic of its nature has been protecting us from calamities, floods and storms for centuries. Despite all invasions and conquests, the fact that our ancestors did not lose their identity, followed the standards of moral life, and strived for perfection even today is an example and gives strength to all of us. It is known that the thinking, way of life, and spiritual views of any people or nation are not formed by themselves, in a vacuum. We all know that their emergence and development are based on

specific historical, natural and social factors. For example, in the Eastern world, including in our own Uzbekistan, the feeling of living together as a community is very important and creates a basis for bringing people closer to each other, supporting and supporting each other. In this sense, if we look at the way of life and thinking of our people, we see a number of unique features that are not like others, have been formed over thousands of years, and are manifested not only in mutual interaction, but also as an integral part of our life. This means that the above-mentioned qualities of our people are of particular importance in the consistent implementation of the reforms carried out in our country. It is not an exaggeration to say that the actions carried out in our country are surprising the entire world public at a time when various tensions are arising within the social, economic, cultural, spiritual and political landscape of the world. Unfortunately, we are witnessing the formation of new traditions and customs, as well as a character that is completely foreign to us, that were introduced to our country during the process of adhering to the principles of openness in the foreign policy of our country. It is natural to observe such events in the process of globalization. The famous Indian statesman Mahatma Gandhi said to the globalization process: "I cannot keep the gates and doors of my house closed all the time, because fresh air must enter my house." At the same time, I don't want the air coming in through the open doors and windows to turn my house upside down and knock me down." With this, he puts forward the idea that it is necessary to understand the positive and negative aspects of the globalization process in time and respond to them with ideas and enlightenment. Taking into account that more than 60 percent of the population in our country are Esh, it would be appropriate to spread among the Esh the classic moral rules about the ancient and high spiritual qualities of our people. However, the Uzbek term is equivalent to the Turkish word, meaning self-confident, independent thinker and worker, hero, brave, devout, unyielding. Abdurauf Fitrat also mentions in his tragedy "Abulfayzkhan"

that "Uzbek boys will be heroes". Because today's great results achieved by our people in the fields of sports, science, culture and art in the international fields, we think, prove that they are the heirs of ancestors who created a great and high culture from long ago. At this point, we considered it permissible to enumerate the examples mentioned in the book of the First President Islam Karimov, "High Spirituality - Invincible Power". That is, "If we look at the history of the world, other nations, in the process of gaining freedom and independence, national revival, strengthening their statehood, enviable civil society, relied on such qualities and in all spheres - whether it is economic or social life, whether it is culture, education and science - we see that they have achieved progress due to the use of their unique internal abilities and potential, and their realization. The rest of Japan and South Korea are shown separately. These regions are among the countries with abundant natural resources and very few mineral resources. Nevertheless, it is not a secret to anyone today that the Japanese and Korean people have developed over the centuries due to their unique national spirituality, which has become a great creative force. Therefore, when talking about "Japanese miracle" or "Korean miracle", the experts of the international economy first of all mention the expressions "Japanese character", "Korean nature". The next five years were the period when new and modern innovations were implemented in our country. To bring this to our attention, it is enough to bring to our attention the works carried out within the framework of the Strategy of Actions and the Strategy of Development. Ne-ne has experienced many trials in history; Our people, who have no equal in patience and contentment, are working valiantly in all fields, showing their true character and nature in the period of changes that are sweeping over our country. Our government is carrying out reforms based on the will of our people. At this point, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyev said, "Our main achievement is the ability of our multi-ethnic nation to overcome any difficulties and trials, its modern outlook, political

consciousness and social activity are on the rise, it is not indifferent to the events around us, but lives with a sense of belonging" [1: 286] - he emphasizes. Of course, within the framework of ensuring the effectiveness of these reforms, we must emphasize that our people have united around the idea of entrepreneurship put forward by our government.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that in the mentality of the Uzbek people, there are common aspects for all social strata, which require the development of many qualities that protect the interests of the community. The qualities of tolerance, hospitality, peace-loving, mutual cooperation, mutual understanding in times of joy and sorrow, comradeship in the internal character of our people were born and refined from the need to ensure collective unanimity, language and language, unity of thought. It should also be said that one of the most important aspects of the intellectual and spiritual quality of our people is the extreme respect for science, special attention to education and profession. It is of particular importance that the unique positive aspects of our people are at the root of the huge changes implemented in our country.

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